

Theoretical investigation of structural, electronic, optical and thermoelectric properties of GaAgO₂ based on Density Functional Theory (DFT): Two approach

Md. Rajib Munshi ^{1,*}, Md. Zuel Rana ¹, Sapan Kumar Sen ², Md. Ruhul Amin Faisal ³ and Md. Hazrat Ali ⁴

¹ Department of Physics, Faculty of Science of Engineering, European University of Bangladesh, Gabtoli, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

² Institute of Electronics, Atomic Energy Research Establishment, Bangladesh Atomic Energy Commission, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

³ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science of Engineering, European University of Bangladesh, Gabtoli, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

⁴ Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering, Faculty of Science of Engineering, European University of Bangladesh, Gabtoli, Dhaka, Bangladesh.

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Abstract

In this research we have investigated systematically, the structural, electronic, bonding, optical, thermodynamic aspects of the GaAgO₂ crystal using first-principles computations based on the density functional theory (DFT). To begin, the bandgap energies of GaAgO₂ crystal have estimated to be 0.640 eV and 0.768 eV using the Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) based on the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) and Revised Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (RPBE) functional methods. The density of state and partial density of state of GaAgO₂ were then simulated to determine the nature of the orbital of the Ga, Ag, and O atoms. The Mulliken population charge and electron density distributions have estimated to further elucidate the bonding nature of GaAgO₂. The complex dielectric function, refractive index, reflectivity, absorption coefficient, loss function, and photoconductivity of GaAgO₂ are all computed and analyzed in depth for the optical transitions. Additionally, come to the realization of it, the thermo-electronic and thermophysical features have been added to enable this crystal to absorb visible light and retain a stable thermal state, enabling them to be employed in optoelectronic devices such as lasers, solar cells, and even luminescence ones.

Keywords: Band gap; Electronic structure; DOS; PDOS; Optical; Thermodynamic properties

1. Introduction

Semiconductors materials have experienced significant extensive research in the past several decades, because of their distinct characteristics and potential industrial uses for which they hold great promise [1-2]. Recently, semiconductors have garnered considerable study attention owing to their exceptional thermal and chemical durability [3], as well as their unique structural, morphological, optical, and catalytic features [4-5]. It has immense applications in electronic technology [6], power devices [7], nanospintronic devices [8-9], transistors [10], photo-sensors [11], microcontrollers [12] and integrated circuits [13]. In the contemporary era, most of the electronic technologies and optoelectronic devices solely depend on using of semiconductor materials due to their chemical, physical, thermo-electronic properties [14], good chemical stability [15-16] and optical characters [17], gas sensing [18], environmental purification [19], therapeutic material [20], element in photovoltaic cells [21] and so on. Furthermore, due to their inexpensive cost and availability, modifications to their chemical structures have been developed to make them more environmentally

* Corresponding author: Md. Rajib Munshi

Department of Physics, Faculty of Science of Engineering, European University of Bangladesh, Gabtoli, Dhaka-1216, Bangladesh.

friendly and non-toxic [22–23] and liquid crystals have been developed for more flexible implementations in modern technologies [24–26]. Meanwhile, obtaining a high-efficiency semiconductor at room temperature utilizing group II–IV metals is a monumental constraint because to the variety of suitable moods [27–30]. Among these flaws, the atomic size, broad band gap, and low cost are the most important for developing novel semiconductor materials, despite the fact that they have a significant impact on the ability to absorb or emit ultraviolet (UV) light in optoelectronic applications [31–32]. Moreover, Gallium crystals or gallium oxides have been proved to be promising candidates for transparent electronics, chemical and gas sensors, optoelectronic devices and UV emitters with a large band gap [33–34] and in a variety of structural configurations the increased demand for silver-based alloys has prompted researchers to investigate and develop novel materials with acceptable thermochemical characteristics [35–37]. In accordance to these intentions Gallium oxide alloy including Ag metals with formula GaAgO_2 has been designed to investigate structural geometry, electronic structure, Mulliken population, electron charge density, optical and thermo-electronic properties Using computational methods. Although Ga and Ag atoms have been favored owing to their smaller atomic size, which facilitates electronic transitions from the valence band to the conduction band and the generation of a significant number of free electrons, oxygen creates more free electrons than Ga and Ag atoms in the GaAgO_2 crystal. The first principle technique has been used to conduct a systematic study of the structural geometry, electronic structure, Mulliken population, electron charge density, optical characteristics, thermo-electronic, properties of GaAgO_2 in this research. Finally, GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE functional have been applied to perform a comparison investigation in order to acquire a more precise magnitude and acceptability of the compounds. It is anticipated that this research will significantly contribute to gaining a thorough understanding of this material and will serve as a guide for its applications.

2. Computational methods

The GGA with PBE is based on the CASTEP code from Material Studio version 17.1.0.48 has been used to calculate band structure, the total density of state (DOS) and the partial density of state (PDOS), because it is suspected to be the most accurate and reliable approach to find out electronic structure and structural features [38]. In this case, the density of state and band structure have been calculated using the cutoff at 510 eV and k point at $2 \times 2 \times 1$ with norm-conserving pseudopotentials. The Electron charge density distribution, optical properties, such as reflectivity, absorption, refractive index, dielectric function, conductivity, and loss function, as well as thermoelectric properties such as enthalpy, heat capacity, entropy, specific heat, mechanical properties have all been simulated in the same way. Moreover, geometrical optimization is completed prior to energy calculations and the atom-force convergence threshold is set at 3×10^{-6} eV/Å. The maximum displacement is at 1×10^{-3} Å and the total energy and the maximal stress are at 1×10^{-5} eV/atom and 5×10^{-2} GPa, respectively. The another common method, such as Generalized Gradient Approximation (GGA) with Revised Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof functional (RPBE), also has been investigated using required cut-off energy at the same condition.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optimized structure

The lattice parameters are $a = 3.03060 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 3.03060 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 12.36920 \text{ \AA}$ and angles between them are $\alpha = 90.000 \text{ \AA}$, $\beta = 90.000 \text{ \AA}$, $\gamma = 120.000 \text{ \AA}$. The monoclinic GaAgO_2 crystal and the area cluster which is Hermann Mauguin P63/mmc [194], hexagonal crystals system, point cluster 6/mmm, Hall-P 6c 2c, density 6.04 g/cm³ are shown in Figure 1(a) and 1(b).

3.2. Electronic structure

The Fermi level has been set to zero in order to determine the electronic band structures of GaAgO_2 using GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE. As shown in Figure 2(a), between the K and M symmetry points, the minimum of conduction bands (MCB) is settled, while the maximum of valence bands (MVB) is sited at the H symmetry point. For GaAgO_2 utilizing GGA with PBE method, the symmetry point is observed at different MCB and MVB locations, which is referred to as the indirect band gap, with values obtained of 0.640 eV.

The highest levels of the valence band around the H symmetry point, on the other hand, are dispersive, although not as dispersive as the upper regions of GaAgO_2 . Using a lower effective mass carrier, it is possible to identify materials that might be used in high-mobility electronic devices [39]. GGA with RPBE has been shown to calculate band gaps under the same conditions and the accompanying visual views are provided in Figure 2. (b), which demonstrates that the band gaps for GaAgO_2 are both indirect with magnitudes of 0.768. By analyzing the accompanying figures, it is plausible to

extrapolate that all band gaps for GaAgO₂ are deemed indirect band gap and the values are nearly identical for the two approaches. The comparison values for the optimum situation are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1 (a) Structure of GaAgO₂ (Ball and stick) and (b) Structure of GaAgO₂ (Polyhedral)

Figure 2 (a, b) Electronic band structure of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE method respectively

Table 1 Comparative bandgaps for GaAgO₂

Compound Name	Analysis Method	
	GGA with PBE	GGA with RPBE
GaAgO ₂	0.640 eV	0.768 eV

3.3. Mulliken atomic population

To have a deeper understanding about the bonding properties of GaAgO₂, the Mulliken atomic population [40-41] is computed and listed in Table 2. Moreover, this research provides credible information on bond overlap and charge transfer between the various sorts of atoms in a material. As seen in Table 2, the Ga and Ag atoms have a positive charge, whereas the O atoms have a negative charge for the GaAgO₂ material. As a result, charge transfer occurs between Ga and Ag atoms and the O atom. Our computations are similar with those of prior theoretical investigations of a similar kind [42].

Table 2 Population analysis of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE approach

Analysis	Mulliken									Hirshfeld
	Compound	Species	s	p	d	Total	Charge (e)	Bond	Population	Lengths (Å)
GaAgO ₂	Ga	0.56	0.95	10.00	11.51	1.49	0 - Ga	0.75	2.0105	0.45
	Ag	2.70	6.31	9.81	18.82	0.18	0 - Ag	0.27	2.1019	0.28
	O	1.84	5.00	0.00	6.84	-0.84				-0.36

3.4. Density of states and partial density of state

The DOS and PDOS have been used to investigate the properties of electronic band structures and orbital dispersion. The DOS and PDOS of Ga, Ag, and O elements have been determined for GaAgO₂ crystals using the GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE approach. Figure 3(a, b) and 3(c, d) depicts the simulation of DOS and PDOS for GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE approach. The nature of 3d¹⁰, 4s² and 4p¹ for Ga; 4p⁶, 4d¹⁰ and 5s¹ for Ag; and 2s² and 2p⁴ for O elements have been studied to explain the transition of electrons due to hybridization by traveling from the maximum valence band (MCB) to the minimum conduction band (MCB). The p-orbital dominates the conduction band, while the d-orbital contributes the most to the formation of the valence band. The 4p¹ orbital is almost vacant in Ga, which causes it to migrate toward the conduction band; nevertheless, the p-orbital is partly filled by 2p⁴ orbitals for O-atoms and 4d¹⁰ and 5s¹ orbitals for Ag-atoms. As a consequence, the conduction band's greatest peak for PDOS is obtained from the combined contribution of p-orbital at around 2.4 eV and s-orbital at approximately 5.7 eV. Additionally, the PDOS of p-orbitals in the conduction band is identical to the DOS pattern. As a consequence, the conduction band is composed of 4p¹ Ga, 4d¹⁰ and 5s¹ of Ag and 2p⁴ O-atoms, while the valence band is composed of a combination of p- and d-orbitals. The maximum electron intensity or density in the valence band is around 13.0 electrons/eV, while d-orbital electrons account for almost 8.4 electrons/eV and p orbital accounts for 4.6 electrons/eV. The s-orbital and p-orbital have a higher electron density in the conduction band.

Figure 3 (a, b) Total DOS and PDOS of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE method (c, d) Total DOS and PDOS of GaAgO₂ in GGA with RPBE method (e, f) PDOS of GaAgO₂ for Ga and Ag atom in GGA with PBE method (g, h)) PDOS of GaAgO₂ for Ga and Ag atom in GGA with RPBE method

3.5. Electron charge density

The electron charge density distribution of GaAgO₂ crystal provide valuable information about its chemical bonding characteristics. Hence we determined the charge density map of GaAgO₂ in 3D visualization and along (100) plane using GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE approach and illustrated the result in fig 4(a, b) and (c, d). The electron charge density distribution of the GaAgO₂ crystal reveals important details regarding its chemical bonding properties. It is generally recognized that when the electron clouds of two atoms overlap and the electrons consolidate in the overlapping region, a covalent bond is formed between them. There is indeed a significant overlap of electron clouds between Ga and O atoms in the figure, which validates the existence of sigma type Ga-O covalent bonds in GaAgO₂. There is no overlapping of charge distribution among Ag atoms viewing the ionic character of Ag - Ag bond. The ionic nature is the consequence of the metallic character [43] showing the metallic feature of Ag - Ag Bonds Overall, the investigation of the density of states, Mulliken atomic population, and the total charge density of GaAgO₂ is comprehensive.

Figure 4 Electronic charge density (a) 3 D View and (b) along 100 plane of GaAgO₂ (c) 3 D View and (d) along 100 plane of GaAgO₂

3.6. Optical properties

Indeed, optical characteristics of solids are a valuable tool for studying energy band structure, excitations, impurity levels, localized defects, and lattice vibrations, among other things. To prosecute the optical properties of GaAgO₂ crystals absorption, refractive index, dielectric function $\epsilon(\omega)$, optical conductivity, and loss function have been explored. Reflectivity, absorption, refractive index, dielectric function $\epsilon(\omega)$, optical conductivity, and loss function have all been depicted in such studies. The complex conductivity or frequency-dependent complex dielectric function $\epsilon(\omega)$, is intimately connected to the energy band structure of solids.

3.6.1. Optical reflectivity

However, since electron delocalization processes can lead to an insulator-to-metal transition, the formation of periodically spaced vacancy layers inside the meta-stable phase of Ga-Ag-O₂ phase-change materials has recently been getting a lot of attention. Several earlier investigations have shown that a lower reflectivity corresponds to a greater UV or visible light absorption [44–45]. In Figure 5(a) the optical reflectivity is illustrated in GGA with PBE method and it is seen that the reflectivity of GaAgO₂ starts at around 0.32 from the initial frequency. Afterwards the the reflectivity of GaAgO₂ changes roughly before 2.5 eV and gradually increased after 2.5 eV. In addition, for GaAgO₂ reflectivity increases to about 0.47 and then starts to fall for the corresponding frequency at about 3.8 eV. In Figure 5(b) the optical reflectivity is illustrated in GGA with RPBE method and from Figures 5(a) and 5(b), it is observed that the value of reflectivity is highly lower compared to the absorption.

Figure 5 Optical reflectivity of GaAgO₂ (a) GGA with PBE and (b) GGA with RPBE methods

3.6.2. Absorption

The polycrystalline polarization technique has been used to compute the optical absorbance of GaAgO₂, and a modest smearing value of 0.1 was used to obtain more distinct absorbance peaks. Figure 6(a) the absorption peak of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE method shows that absorbance peaks are created at various photon energies where electronic transitions from MVB to MCB occur as a result of incident light (visible). In this case, the absorption increases slowly from 0.5 to 2.0 eV and then decreases until 2.5 eV and increases dramatically after that. In Figure 6(b) the absorption peak has shown in GGA with RPBE method. As this GaAgO₂ material has a reduced band gap and better absorption, as well as a wide range of photon energy absorption capabilities soon after the beginning point, it might be employed to make various optical communication and optoelectronic device applications devices [46-47].

Figure 6 Optical absorption of GaAgO₂ (a) GGA with PBE and (b) GGA with RPBE methods

3.6.3. Refractive Index

Figure 7 Refractive index of GaAgO₂ (a) GGA with PBE and (b) GGA with RPBE methods

The refractive index, which refers to the relationship between the speed of light in a vacuum and the speed of light in another medium, implies that a greater refractive index indicates a denser material or less absorption. In Figure 7(a), the refractive index as a function of photon energy seems to have been determined using the GGA with PBE approach. It is composed of two components: real and imaginary, and may be defined as the ratio of the speed of light in free space to the speed of light in another medium. The greater the value of the real component, the more suitable it is for use in optoelectronic devices; conversely, the greater the value of the imaginary portion, the less suitable it is for use in

optoelectronic devices. The refractive index of GaCuO₂ is greater in the real portion at the origin of photon energy, but the imaginary part is nearly zero. The real parts of the refractive index follow a rather steady pattern with rising photon energy up to 2.75 eV, after which they gradually drop with increasing photon energies. The refractive index as a function of photon energy has been seen another common method GGA with RPBE in figure 7(b).

3.6.4. Dielectric function

For investigating the optical characteristics of a material the dielectric function is the most influential tool, which are connected with adsorption properties for solids as indicated in the following equation: $(\omega) = \epsilon_1(\omega) + i\epsilon_2(\omega)$, Here, $\epsilon_1(\omega)$ and $\epsilon_2(\omega)$ are represented the dielectric constant (real part) and the dielectric loss factor (imaginary part), respectively. The dielectric function is associated with the physical space of materials that are physically compatible with absolute permittivity or permittivity. The real component of the dielectric function represents the capacity of dielectric materials to store energy in an electric field, while the imaginary part represents the ability of dielectric materials to dissipate energy. The dielectric properties of GaAgO₂ crystals in GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE are shown in Figure 8(a, b). It is clear that, for GaAgO₂ crystals, the real parts of the dielectric function illustrate the larger magnitude than imaginary part meaning that it can be highly used as an electrostatic cell as energy storage materials.

Figure 8 Refractive index of GaAgO₂ (a) GGA with PBE and (b) GGA with RPBE methods

3.6.5. Conductivity

Conduction in semiconductors based on energy bands and orbital electrons is related to the distinct orbital space of electrons. In semiconductors, conduction occurs as a result of the existence of holes and free electrons in the crystal molecules. Figure 9(a, b) demonstrates that the conductivity of GaAgO₂ material in GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE method. The real parts increase slowly up to 2.5 eV and after then increase sharply whereas the imaginary parts decrease following opposite direction with little variation at the end portion. It is also observed that the upper peak of the conductivity reaches about 6.77 1/fs at 3.6 eV for of GaAgO₂. Finally, it was rebuilding that GaAgO₂ crystal has a good conductivity.

Figure 9 Conductivity of GaAgO₂ (a) GGA with PBE and (b) GGA with RPBE methods

3.6.6. Loss function

The energy curve is used to establish the zones of high and low energy. The first region accounts for the large energy loss with frequency or spectrum shift after an ionizing edge, sometimes referred to as the oxidation state of d-orbital splitting for atomic metals in complex compounds with a range higher than 3.5 eV. The other is a low energy loss function with an energy loss of less than 3.0 eV that may be used to determine the composition and electronic structure of a material. The loss function for GaAgO₂ crystals is shown in figure 10(a) for GGA with PBE and 10(b) for GGA with RPBE. As seen in the figure, GaAgO₂ has a higher energy loss in the low energy zone due to its electronic structure and composition. On the other hand, the loss function in the higher energy region steadily rose, indicating that there is no difference in d-orbital splitting.

Figure 10 Loss function of GaAgO₂ (a) GGA with PBE and (b) GGA with RPBE methods

3.7. Thermoelectric Properties

Thermoelectric features include heat transfer through electronic transitions in physical and chemical processes [48], energy transfer via biological and chemical processes [49], and system-environment interaction. The fundamental concepts of thermodynamics are entropy, heat capacity, enthalpy, and free energy, which enable the interaction of physics and physical chemistry in every system. According to Petersen et al., entropy and enthalpy are tightly related, and entropy provides information on a substance's discharge state. Figure 11(a, b) illustrates the total comparison of thermophysical properties of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE methods.

3.7.1. Entropy

Entropy is a significant concept in physics and chemistry, as well as in a variety of other fields of study. It is a component of cosmology and economics, as well as a key component of thermodynamics and physical chemistry. It is a metric for the dysfunctional state of a system. Additionally, it gives the one-of-a-kind property of a thermodynamic system, in which the value fluctuates in proportion to the quantity of matter present. Entropy is commonly symbolized by the letter *S* in equations (1) and (2) and has units of joules per Kelvin (J K⁻¹) or kg m² S⁻² K⁻¹. A highly ordered system has low entropy. Figure 11 (a, b) shows the Entropy of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE method. From figure 10(a) it is clear that at 1000 K, with the highest upper entropy at 1.28 eV for GaAgO₂. It has been demonstrated that increasing the temperature increases the entropy of GaAgO₂ crystals. As a result, it is possible to assert that the GaAgO₂ material exhibits less disordered behavior or molecular disruptions.

3.7.2. Heat capacity

The heat capacity of a body is the amount of energy necessary to increase its temperature by a certain amount. The current force has an effect on a material's heat capacity, which complicates the calculation of a material's kinetic energy. Thermal properties of an alloy might be significantly different from those of its individual components. As seen in Figure 11(c) in GGA with PBE method, total heat capacity of GaAgO₂ has improved gradually since its inception, making it an outstanding material for optoelectronic devices. The heat capacity in GGA with RPBE technique has been illustrated in 11(d).

3.7.3. Enthalpy

Enthalpy is a thermodynamic feature that relates to both the capacity for non-mechanical work and the capacity for heat release. The enthalpy is calculated using the following formula.

$$H = E + PV \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

$$dH = TdS + PdV \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Here, H is enthalpy, E is the internal energy of the system, P is pressure and V is volume. From The enthalpy of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE and GaAgO₂ in GGA with RPBE method have illustrated in figure 11 (a, b) and it is found that with increasing the temperature from 100 to 1000 K, the change of enthalpy obtained from zero to 3.22 eV respectively, for the GaAgO₂.

3.7.4. Free Energy

The quantity of internal energy in a thermodynamic system that may be used to do work is referred to as free energy. the thermodynamic properties like free energy of GaAgO₂ have been listed in Figure 11(a, b) in GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE methods. Finally, in our research, we discovered that the free energy of GaAgO₂ begins at the energy level zero eV at 100 K. The free energy gradually decreased with increase of temperature and maximum lower free energy obtained 1.92 eV at 1000 k. It could be concluded that the thermophysical properties such as entropy, heat capacity, enthalpy, and free energy of GaAgO₂ at different temperatures have been compared in Tables 3.

Figure 11 (a, b) Thermodynamic properties of GaAgO₂ in GGA with PBE and) GGA with RPBA methods comparison, (c, d) Total heat capacity

Table 3 Thermophysical properties of GaAgO₂ at different temperatures in GGA with PBE method

Compound Name	Temperature (K)	Entropy (eV/ K)	Heat capacity (eV/K)	Enthalpy (eV/K)	Free Energy (eV/K)
GaAgO ₂	105.50	0.027	15.108	0.040	-0.013
	276.36	0.196	27.185	0.358	-0.162
	407.02	0.357	29.477	0.722	-0.364
	597.97	0.607	30.674	1.361	-0.753
	798.98	0.877	31.157	2.130	-1.252
	1000	1.150	31.384	2.970	-1.820

4. Conclusion

On the basis of density function theory, we have estimated extensive physical properties of GaAgO₂ CASTEP code, including structural, electrical, chemical bonding, optical, thermodynamic properties. The estimated lattice parameters accord well with each other. While gallium crystals or oxides have been developed as a material with a large band gap for use in optoelectronic devices, it has revealed that GaAgO₂ has been assessed as a material with a narrow band gap. Initially, utilizing GGA and the PBE method, a band gap of 0.640 eV has been obtained. Second, a functional analysis of GGA with RPBE was done for comparative purposes, yielding a value of 0.768 eV. The electronic band gap is smaller, as shown by changes in DOS and PDOS data, but the total sum of DOS is considerably bigger. As a consequence, GGA with PBE and GGA with RPBE have a closer band gap. The Mulliken atomic populations and total charge density demonstrate that all of the compounds have ionic, covalent, and metallic bonds. The absorption quality is excellent in visible and UV. However, the entropy and free energy values for GaAgO₂ are somewhat inverted, indicating a chemically and thermally less stable crystal at high temperatures. According to the definitive proof of absorption, reflectivity, loss function, and conductivity, GaAgO₂ is the best material to use in optoelectronic devices.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors hereby declare there is no conflict of interest.

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